

ENGLISH TEACHING METHODOLOGY TERMS AND THEIR EQUIVALENTS IN UZBEKI

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Abstract: *This article provides an analysis of pedagogical terms in English and Uzbek languages, information about the role of terms in technology, science, art and social life.*

Key words: *pedagogical term, assessment, translation, terminology, dictionary.*

As you know, English is currently the main language of communication in the world. Thus, the English language is evolving by constantly adding new words to its vocabulary. The influence of the English language on the Uzbek language is very large and it can be seen mainly in various fields of science, pedagogy, technology and social life. In many cases, we came from the English language based on the internal capabilities of the Uzbek language we try to find the equivalent of the term. But there are terms that are sold as international terms (or international words), which are used in the same form in English and Uzbek without any changes. For example, Greek and Latin words are widely used as technical and scientific terms. As A. Avloni said: "Education is life for us. It is a matter of death, salvation, destruction, happiness or health. In fact, the place of education is very important in human life, happiness and pure human activity. It is known that educating the young generation is the main task of our work, and this is a positive result for us, therefore, we must train them in the spirit of loyalty to our nation, our nation we need to educate. To achieve this, first of all, we need to inculcate concepts such as national pride, national pride, spirituality, national ideal,

etc. in the minds of the young generation. After all, it is certainly impossible to dream of a bright future without knowing and learning the history of the people, the mother tongue, and receiving spiritual nourishment from them. Behbudi, Avloni, Ainiy, Munavar Qori, Hamza and others greeted students opened new branches in Orenburg and Srim. They learned the methods and methods of teaching Russian language and adapted them to their conditions. Thus, the first textbooks and manuals for these schools were created and this for the first time, special terms related to education were included in the books. The new pedagogical term is related to the study of the lexical field in all languages. The ability to form new terms according to the quality of the language and the level of development of models and methods of word formation. Let's look at the division of pedagogical terms. Pedagogical terms are divided into two groups: Terms of educational theory. The conditions of the educational system, the subject, the nature of education, the subject of study. Terms of educational theory. Education, educator, moral education, laboratory education. According to scientific studies of linguistics, the number of pedagogical terms is more than ten thousand. In addition, it should be noted that pedagogical terms in English and Uzbek are divided into several groups: Terms representing pedagogical concepts: school, institute, lesson, practice, method, pedagogy, exam, book, etc. Names of persons related to education: teacher, head of class, restaurant, vice restaurant, dean. Legal terms are widely used in Uzbek and English pedagogy. For example, the National Anthem (National Anthem) is one of the important symbols of an independent state and is a solemn and musical composition usually performed on a special occasion. State grant (State grant) - Paid funds are allocated for the financial support of scientists, scholars, authors of art and literature. A grant is support for carrying out scientific research and is not a repayable loan. A state grant is a grant paid for the study of students at universities funded by the state. The State Education Standard (State Education Standard) is a document on the main foci of the basic requirements for

education. The 21st century is the age of information and technologies. Therefore, at present, it is the image of pedagogical pedagogy and educational process without innovative technologies spread out. Therefore, everyone working in the educational system should know how to use computer technologies and educational materials in the teaching process. In conclusion, pedagogy cannot be imagined without special terms. Terms are highly imported during testing. With their help, the educational process will be more effective and understandable. The importance of the English language should also be noted here.

List of used literature:

1. Yusupova S.A. Translation of pedagogical terms into English and Uzbek languages, English and Uzbek terminology. 2021 year
2. Kh. Paluanova, M. Musumonova, K. Riskulova, Z. Qurbanniyozova. "List of pedagogical terms" 11/16/2012.
3. Abdullaeva Marhabo Rahmonkulovna. (2021). Translation from English to Uzbek and its characteristics. Innovation, integration and education international journal, 2 (2).